

Safeguarding the digital single market's e-commerce ecosystem ENSURESEC develops an automatic, rigorous, distributed and open-source toolkit

The consortium of 22 partners from 14 European countries is working together on a comprehensive security toolkit for e-commerce platforms that offers both suppliers and end customers effective protection for their data and products. This way, the project aims to contribute to the European vision of a reliable and trusted Digital Single Market.

As a socio-technical solution for the e-commerce activities of the European Digital Single Market, ENSURESEC combines the toolkit, including cyber-physical threat monitoring and impact assessment, with a large-scale training and awareness campaign to educate e-commerce SMEs and citizens on cyber-security and improve the resilience of the ecosystem.

At the technical level of the toolkit, state-of-the-art tools and techniques are integrated into a platform so that e-commerce operations are protected both by design and through continuous monitoring, response, recovery, and mitigation measures at run-time. Latest generation distributed ledger technology provides a complete audit trail of security incidents, as well as a decentralized identity management system, ensuring trust and transparency of operations, and immutability of information.

The final toolkit will analyze if an e-commerce infrastructure is secure against certain types of critical attacks and it will monitor the infrastructure to identify new vulnerabilities and threats. In the event of an outsider's attack, the ENSURESEC solution will help affected users and e-commerce providers to respond to the incident, mitigate its impact, and recover normal operation.

The technical teams are working closely with selected end users covering the full range of the e-commerce ecosystem, to match the project's potential capabilities with the actual needs of practitioners. The close collaboration in these tasks allowed the consortium members to gather all the requirements and data needed to define credible scenarios for the project's use cases, which address the whole gamut of e-commerce operations: Pilot 1 – Cyber-attacks on e-commerce platform; Pilot 2 – Physical attacks on pharmacy e-commerce operator and Pilot 3 – Cascading cyber-physical attacks on e-commerce.

Besides creating technical solutions, improving awareness is an important part of the project. ENSURESEC is currently developing a campaign to train e-commerce users as well as employees of SMEs and other e-commerce operators with a set of serious games, and by visualizing the cascading effects of impacts, which would have been avoidable with better security measures and improved awareness.

More Information

Website – <https://www.ensuresec.eu/>

LinkedIn – [ENSURESEC](#)

Twitter – [ensuresec_eu](#)

E-mail – ensuresec@inov.pt

About ENSURESEC

ENSURESEC is an ongoing project in the EU Horizon 2020 programme under the topic [SU-INFRA01-2018-2019-2020 - Prevention, detection, response and mitigation of combined physical and cyber threats to critical infrastructure in Europe](#), and part of the programmes [H2020-EU.3.7.4. - Improve cyber security](#) and [H2020-EU.3.7.2. - Protect and improve the resilience of critical infrastructures, supply chains and transport modes](#). The project, with 22 partners from all over Europe, has an overall budget of 9.2 Million Euro and has received a funding contribution from the EU of 7.7 Million Euro. ENSURESEC started on June 1st 2020 and will end on May 31st 2022, and it is coordinated by INOV from Portugal.

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